

ALIXON TORA SOGUNIY

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Anantation: *In this article you will learn about the life of Alikhan Tora and about escape from prison, and its role in the formation of ETR (East Turkestan Revolution). creations and books.*

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Today we decided to tell you about a scholar known among the people as Alixontora soguni, a political public figure known as the Uzbek marsha, as well as a doctor who treated cancer infertility. The autobiography of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him), whose real name is Alikhantora Soguni, was written in March 1885 in the Uzbek city of Tokmak, Kyrgyzstan. Alikhanto'ra's brother, along with Alimkhan, took him to Mecca to improve his religious education. There he studied Alikhanto'ra's theology, hadith, and logical Arabic-Persian. According to sources, he studied in Mecca and later

In Jeddah between 1905 and 1915. He returned to Uzbekistan to study not only Islam but also Oriental medicine. He continued his education in Bukhara. He taught Islam at a local madrasa in Bukhara. Several Uzbek-language social media sites quoted the Uzbek National Encyclopedia as strongly opposed to the Tsarist government's oppression of the local population. police persecution 1916 brutally suppressed anti-labor uprising Political immigrants left for Kashgar China and then went to the city of East Turkestan The Uzbek national liberation movement is said to have escaped from a prison where the former Soviet government was imprisoned four times for its benevolence to the oppressive movement.

Among them, he was arrested by Chinese authorities in 1937 and sentenced to life imprisonment for promoting the ideas of freedom. He was released in 1941 as a result of a judicial review. He lived in Tashkent until the end of his life. He died in Tashkent on February 18, 1976 and was presented to the Tashkent khan. Muhammad is proud to recall that his grandson was the favorite grandson of the people who reached the publishing house through the efforts of a 60-year-old hero. The history of Muhammad has been published five times since 1988, and with the

help of Master Abdulaziz Mansur, who wrote letters in many places, he published and delivered to the people before his death. In recent years, there have been people who predicted the independence of Uzbekistan. I don't see the end of it for us children, but you will see that 1527 Uzbekistan will be an independent state and the state will disintegrate. Another room that was forbidden by the ummah was oriental medicine.

To prove it, he cites the following example: He was a famous athlete in his time. He was a Soviet champion in sports. An 11-year-old girl was brought in by her father, who had a large tumor on her head and was diagnosed with throat cancer. They couldn't find any cure. They told us to leave the mother and child in the room. In less than a month, the girl had a sore throat. She had a big tumor on her head. Unfortunately, in the book of doctors written by my grandfather, who was not able to continue what he had been forced to do, the great political and military activity of the entire population was promoted by the idea of independent Turkestan. According to historical sources, he was the President of the Republic of East Turkestan, which was re-established after the revolution in 1944, and was of Uzbek descent.

I was a bride in that house, I was a bride, I was a bride. We can bring a famous figure first, a scientist, a politician, a statesman, a writer, a historian, a liar, very wide, 1990, when Uzbekistan first became independent It is known that for 97 years the second book was published in Turkestan. I don't know why I became a bride in that house. And even people like Shermuhammadbek got to know each other better from Alikhantor's Sogdian books. A lot of information about their lives was given to them by fate. It is forbidden to talk about Surat al-Ahl, as long as what we know about him is forbidden. When I came to Turkey, I started studying at the Marble University. I wanted to write a biography of Alikhan Tura. I wrote about so many types of Alikhan Tura Sogani. Alikhantora Soguni's political activities are not known, but we know them from many books, but Alihontora Soguni's very political life speaks of them from childhood.

They come back a few years later, even a year later, but those who continue to work will still be able to accept the Chilean faith. The central machine will be more profitable. As a nation, people who accept their language in such a situation, who pay attention to one thing every Friday. Those who skillfully used the saying that a nation could easily own its own nest, that is, those who fled several times during the period of policy and a few silent alhan types but gradually increased persecution, went to different places, for example, from 1917 onwards in which

Turkestan works of that period In the play, Koramiza, who was imprisoned many times and fled to East Turkestan after his many escapes, returned to East Turkestan at the age of forty-five for the last time. Documents that date back to the Xinjiang region of present-day Turkestan, where the main activities began at that time. There is no doubt that there was a time when the British set themselves a goal, but it will not increase, but those who did not pay attention to the transition to East Turkestan, which was a time of struggle to see the connection, will be very hungry.

He wrote that it was very easy to find so many goods in East Turkestan, and that the Soviet Union, which intended to make East Turkestan its own in order to make itself known to the descendants of those who portrayed such Russians as a mirror, was now the Soviet Union. The economy of the Islamic Republic of Turkestan was led by Notami, a republic that had been active for only a year. We know that those who were released after his interrogations were a notable party in 1938, but we know that in the 1930s, when it was introduced into the Soviet Union, it was an Eastern Turk. In 1938, in parallel with a number of Uzbeks, he began to take prisoners in East Turkestan. In 1941, the political situation at the wedding changed for the better, and political prisoners were released. continued his work as.

The army will be formed and given to the 14th, that is, we will see both the pension and the Russian aid books in the books, because their imprisonment ends with information about themselves, but their second son, Askhan, has memories of them. Several recorded encounters, firstly, secondly, then, now, then, now, then, now, then, second, second, second, second, second, second, second, second, first, second, second, first, second, second, second At that time, the Second World War of 1944 was going on, and the Russians did not increase as much as they did when the Soviet Union came to power. There were times in his office when he began to find sympathetic states. Of course, they also worked in East Turkestan. They helped back. They helped. They helped with weapons. They also helped with weapons. The old man's head looked like Soviet uniforms. One of the reasons he went to the army, where he was appointed by the Russian commanders, was one of the reasons why he did not take advantage of the opportunity to take advantage of the opportunity to work with his mother. When there is a region where the increased fiber is not comfortable to live in, the Altai region, where there is a region where the increased fiber is uninhabitable, begins to be refined, that is, where there is a person called a hero. After his death, he joined the measures in a much larger state, until he was even closer to him.

They and the Kashgar side continued to fight on both fronts, both towards the northern construction and towards Kashgar, towards the southern Turkestan. In 1946, aid was stopped abruptly. It is a time of change, and in East Turkestan it was necessary to return to the time when the commission was in power in China, as we understand it will always be there. When they were forcibly brought up in Tashkent one night, it became clear that when we shot their memories, it became clear. In a few days they will receive a letter stating that they will not get better. At that time the republic will go without a leader, and under the pressure of the fiber, their work will go to waste. He was imprisoned for the rest of his life in Tashkent, but he lived in peace since then. He continued his medical work until the end of his life. He was always a student for months and taught medicine.

In the first year of its existence, when the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) opened its doors in the first year of its existence, the Siyar classes were taught in this book. with 54 because our organ at that time found not only their own lives but also a lot of historical information and also very valuable ideas about the importance of learning about the unification of Islam about this organ. He translated poems of Timur in spite of the fact that he was a saver published after his death. The first translation of the work into the Gulistan magazine, even after several issues, was translated into Turkish. They died in Tashkent and were buried in a cemetery on the street.

